

Tetraponera rufonigra (Jerdon, 1851)
a noxious ant species associated with
Aquilaria malacansis cultivation

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A survey was conducted during the year 2023 in three different sasi growing districts of Assam namely Jorhat, Golaghat and Nagaon to study different insect pest associated with *Aquilaria malacansis* (Sasi) one of the most valuable economically important commercialaromatic tree species of North East India. During the survey besides the major pest *Heortia vitessoides*anarboreal bicoloured ant species *Tetraponera rufonigra*locally known as *Mejali* was recorded to be associated with sasi plantation for the first time from all the three sasi growing districts of Assam. The ant species is presumed as a threat by the sasi growing farmers due to the acute pain and inflammation caused by their sting. The ant takes shelter in the cracks and crevices as well as in the tunnels made by *Neurozera conferta* of the aquilaria tree.The actual ecological relationship or interaction of *T. rufonigra* with *A. malacansis* and *Nconferta*however is yet to be established through further research to get a better insight into the complex mechanism of resin formation.